

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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INFORMATIVE-COMMUNICATIVE NATURE OF MASS MEDIA .

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Abstract. It is hard to imagine any area of modern society experiencing the process of globalization without the language of the media. The breadth of media opportunities requires an in-depth study of their activities and development, and their impact on the audience. Media science is a new interdisciplinary field based on traditional methods. The formation of the language of the media is closely linked to their common mission. How viewers perceive information also depends on what tool is used to convey it. Each media uses its own language and methods of updating information to shape its essence, which in turn influences perceptions of existence.

Key words: mass media, communication, mass language, informative tools.

ИНФОРМАТИВНО-КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ ПРИРОДА СМИ.

Аннотация. Трудно представить какую-либо сферу современного общества, переживающую процесс глобализации, без языка средств массовой информации. Широта возможностей СМИ требует глубокого изучения их деятельности и развития, их воздействия на аудиторию. Медиаведение — новая междисциплинарная область, основанная на традиционных методах. Формирование языка СМИ тесно связано с их общей миссией. То, как зрители воспринимают информацию, также зависит от того, какой инструмент используется для ее передачи. Каждое СМИ использует свой язык и методы обновления информации для формирования ее сути, что, в свою очередь, влияет на восприятие существования.

Ключевые слова: средства массовой информации, коммуникация, массовый язык, информационные средства.

Today, the community has a great and fast opportunity to get the latest news through countless media outlets. No matter how information is received, it is expressed through language. Journalism is a creative profession. The journalist must be clear and concise. He is asked to use his thoughts and words in their proper place.

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The status of media language depends on two factors: how we understand the term language and how media language ranks among the functional types of national language.

At present, the language of mass media is the dominant of all functional types of the national language, which includes the resources of all functional styles. In other words, the language of the media today, whether we like it or not, is a composite image of the national language.

Today, the media is recognized as the most effective and acceptable form of speech, an effective mechanism for shaping public opinion and mood.

It is hard to imagine any area of modern society experiencing the process of globalization without the language of the media. Extensive technical capabilities in the media help to express the information provided by the social sphere not only linguistically, but also non-linguistically. As a result, it is also described as the language of science, journalism and culture.

Indeed, the emergence of a single media space in addition to traditional media, radio and television, and the advent of the World Wide Web have led to the emergence of a virtual space with a unique set of media streams. All this is reflected in the formation and distribution of the word, the features of its use in the language change. It is well known that the use of speech is more in the field of mass communication, and its texts, ie media texts, have become one of the most common forms of our language today.

The mass media are mainly used for the following purposes of mass communication:

- 1) informing the audience about what is happening;
- 2) assessment and analysis of events, forecasting their further development;
- 3) assistance in social relations;
- 4) advertising;
- 5) education;
- 6) organization of entertainment events.

The breadth of media opportunities requires an in-depth study of their activities and development, and their impact on the audience. Media science is a new interdisciplinary field based on traditional methods.

Mass media is a common name for the means of conveying information to the general public - periodicals, radio, television and others.

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The formation of the language of the media is closely linked to their common mission. Researchers divide these tasks into the following groups:

- information transmission;
- comment (often the statement of facts is accompanied by their interpretation, analysis and evaluation);
- introduction, teaching and spiritual education (the media serves to replenish the knowledge base of its audience through the transmission of cultural, historical, scientific information);
- the task of influence (the media is not called the fourth power in vain: its influence on public opinion is very strong, which is especially evident in major socio-political processes, including presidential elections);
- the function of entertainment (which means that the media is effectively received by the audience, generates great interest and satisfaction, gives aesthetic pleasure);
- hedonistic feature (this is not just about entertaining information. If any information in the process of transmission evokes a sense of satisfaction and meets the aesthetic needs of the recipient, it is received with great positive effect).

Information is a substantive aspect of communication. Involved in the communication process, it is constantly connected to, influenced, and influenced by the means and networks of storage, collection, distribution, and sorting of information. "Information is, in a sense, 'necessary' information in a message, which is understood by the audience as knowledge, norms, and values, and thus affects the audience."

How viewers perceive information also depends on what tool is used to convey it. Each media uses its own language and methods of updating information to shape its essence, which in turn influences perceptions of existence.

In the process of transmitting and receiving information, interpersonal communication takes place. Communication is, first and foremost, a communicative phenomenon. It is a relationship between one or more individuals that involves mutual understanding and the transfer of information from one person to another or to more than one person.

Mass media:

- 1) psychological features of information reception;
- 2) information features;

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3) values based on the goals set in the process of mass communication activities;

4) theoretical notions of language and text as a means of updating information.

In the process of conveying information in the media, the process of increasing the knowledge of the audience, in a sense, takes place. So what is the mediating role of language in this process of learning?

Language is an important means of communication and expression, and serves as a tool for human beings to systematically and actively understand the world and turn it into an experience. As a result, it is possible to see the world through information and language.

The method and forms of their materialization play an important role in the expression of information through language.

When Wilhelm von Humboldt called the "linguistic landscape of the world" he meant the dynamic, uninterrupted process of assimilating the world through a specific language. According to the German scientist, the "language-defined" conditions of human life should lead to the solution of the tasks associated with the cultural and historical tasks assigned to man. Such people can expand their living space indefinitely.

The social nature of a linguistic community is that, on the one hand, it creates the conditions for coordinated linguistic communication and involves each member in a common and unique process, such as the study of being through language, and on the other hand, it is mandatory for each member. requires that the communication process be "subject to the rules of the game."

Not because people conveyed the meaning of objects to their interlocutors, or even because they were hesitant to clearly and completely recreate a similar concept, but because they co-operated with each other in a chain of emotional imaginations and one of the first manifestations of an inner concept; they understand, because in everyone's mind there is a corresponding but not exactly similar meaning.

These words of Wilhelm von Humboldt reflect the main ideas that reveal the essence of modern linguistic communication. It is important that coordination is closely linked to the individual freedom of each participant as a necessary condition for the communication process.

Linguistic communication, that is, the exchange of information, always requires the creation of specific linguistic forms based on certain models (texts).

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They, in turn, are reflected in the minds of the participants-partners. The dynamics of communication between the two poles requires:

1) a norm that allows for a “similar understanding” of the language units being created, and

2) the need for freedom of choice in such a creative process.

These ideas, expressed by W. Humboldt a century and a half ago, are still very relevant and important today. Communication is indeed a necessary element of cognition, and the communicative beginning is inseparable from the cognitive beginning.

Language, in the first place, motivates one to perform the right action as a result of certain emotions. According to the Austrian philosopher L. V. Witten-Stein, such behavior must have a general effect on the feeling of speakers of a particular language. Language allows a person to perceive the world conventionally (agreed upon, common to all) through words that reflect the experiences of society. This is, in fact, the instrumental function of the word as a symbol. The experience of our ancestors, recorded and systematized in language, shapes a person's perception of the world around him.

It is well known that the division of being into parts takes place differently in each language, because the basis of thought is a language with its own unique national identity.

Conclusion. The role of the media in the uninterrupted flow of language processes is invaluable. This is determined not only by the changes that have taken place as a result of the introduction of new information technologies, but also by the qualitative changes in the general linguistic culture.

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